

Thermoregulation in Layer Poultry

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Introduction

Poultry are warm blooded species (homeothermic), which means they can maintain their body temperature within a certain range. On an average the normal temperature of chicken ranges from 40-42 degree centigrade. The thermal neutral zone for adult laying hens ranges from 18-24 degree centigrade, which means that in this zone the chickens do not need to modify their metabolism to stay warm or to stay cool. Young birds need higher ambient temperatures during the first weeks of their life, because of lack of body reserves (fat), and the ratio of the surface area vs their bodyweight is unfavorable, resulting in heat losses.

Young chick has largest contact body surface with the surrounding air; therefore, they dissipate heat more quickly and cool off much quicker compared to an adult female

When thermal neutral zone is not maintained in the poultry house then birds have several characteristics to maintain their body temperature to keep warm without the production of extra heat. These characteristics include: -

- Birds will huddle together to minimize the loss of heat
- Insulating effect of feathers prevent the loss of heat
- Subcutaneous fat help in insulation
- The dilation and contraction of blood vessels are regulated by chicken and adapt the blood flow through the skin.
- They have ability to increase their body surface to lose more heat

There are many ways to keep cool

Birds regulate their body temperature via hypothalamus (Thermostat). Heat emission and retention is largely affected by dilatation and contraction of blood vessels and the speed of respiration. Birds do not have sweat glands, so they are not able to lose their heat via transpiration. They are able to lose their heat by five different pathways:

- Radiation
 - Conduction
 - Convection
 - Evaporation
 - Vasodilation
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- Sensible heat loss: this is the energy required to change the temperature of a substance with no change of phases.

Chickens are normally able to maintain their normal body temperature of 40-42 degree centigrade via sensible heat loss when the environmental temperature adapt thermal neutral zone of 18-24 degree centigrade.

When the house temperature increases above 25 degree the efficiency of sensible heat loss is going down, and at 35 degree it has hardly any effect unless the relative humidity is low. Management plays a vital role in maintaining your birds' body temperature within their comfort zone.

Proper ventilation helps in heat loss due to convection in poultry house. When the incoming air cooled this improve the radiation. Therefore, the smaller difference between ambient temperature and bird body temperature, possibility of proper heat loss became also poor. Layer birds increase their heat loss by expanding the wings and putting up their feathers so that surrounding air will have maximum contact with their body (especially skin) for heat loss.

Birds can increase their blood circulation in comb, wattles and skin to lose more heat to the cooler surrounding environment (Vasodilation), so dubbing can negatively affect the heat loss and health of bird.

Proper management include supplementation of vitamins and buffer reduce the 15% heat stress. By proper ventilation, incoming of cool air in poultry house will reduce the heat stress about 85%.

Both high temperature and humidity play a key role in mortality of layers due to heat stress, so we have to manage these carefully.

Birds don't have sweat glands so they loss their heat by evaporation (latent heat) by increasing respiration rate. The latent heat of evaporation is the heat required to change water into water

vapor. The water vapor is taking away the heat from the birds' body. This behavior is known as 'panting'. Panting can only be effective when the relative environmental humidity is not too high. The evaporation of 1g of water results in a heat loss of over 500 calories.

Evaporation: Loss of heat by evaporation of water, i.e., the cooling effect of water turning from a liquid to a gas. Fast, shallow breathing with the mouth open helps to increase the loss of body heat.

Vasodilation: Blood increase in the combs and the wattles, lost heat (so do not remove combs).

Radiation: Emission of heat via electromagnetic waves as they transfer energy through the air. Body heat is irradiated to colder objects in the barn, such as the walls or the ceiling of the poultry house.

Convection: The loss of body heat through cold circulating air. Chickens enlarge the exposed surface area by extending their wings away from their bodies. Moving air helps to remove radiated heat as it is creating a cold air effect.

Conduction: Direct transfer of heat via contact with an object of a different temperature, such as the cage wire, floors, litter poultry house and the loss of body heat

Some practical tips which we can implement at low cost to reduce heat stress: -

- Vaccination, transfer, sorting, depopulation all these activities advised to do in the early mornings
- During transportation try to put less birds in crates and place some empty crates in truck/vehicles for proper ventilation. Travel during late night and early morning with less distance is very effective to reduce heat stress among them.
- Do not disturb the birds during hotter parts of the day
- In cage and floor housing system reduce the stocking density so that there will be no or less competition for feed and water which will reduce the heat stress in layers. Cage birds are more susceptible to heat stress as they are not able find cooler place.